

A Systematic Literature Review of Effect Self-Compassion on Students with Learning Disabilities

¹**Dian Atnantomi Wiliyanto**

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7787-4441>

^{2*}**Gunarhadi Gunarhadi**

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1329-6280>

³**Sunardi Sunardi**

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1700-1379>

⁴**Munawir Yusuf**

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0964-2029>

^{1,2,3,4}Doctor of Education Sciences, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta, Indonesia

^{2,3,4}Center of Disability Study, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta, Indonesia

*Correspondence author email: gunarhadi@staff.uns.ac.id

Abstract

Background: Self-compassion is crucial for the well-being of students with impairments. However, only some studies have systematically reviewed its effects on academic and social outcomes.

Objective: This study aimed to examine the influential contributions of self-compassion on the learning experiences of students with impairments, focusing on its potential to enhance academic performance and social well-being.

Methodology: PRISMA guidelines were used to carry out a systematic literature review. The search for pertinent literature was conducted across multiple databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, covering the period from 2016 to 2022. Keywords such as *self-compassion*, *learning disability*, *learning disabilities*, and *effect* were utilised to identify pertinent studies. A total of 13 articles were included in the final analysis.

Results: The findings from the reviewed literature indicate that self-compassion has a significant impact on students with impairments, contributing to (1) enhanced academic achievement, (2) reduced self-criticism, (3) alleviation of stress, depression, anxiety, and loneliness, (4) increased self-confidence, (5) boosted motivation for learning, and (6) improved social well-being. These results underscore self-compassion's strong influence on learning and social engagement for impaired students.

Conclusion: Self-compassion profoundly and positively affects students with impairments' learning and social activities. This study's outcomes provide a foundation for future interventions, therapies, and support services aimed at nurturing self-compassion, enabling these students to reach their full potential.

Unique contribution: This study consolidates evidence highlighting the importance of self-compassion in enhancing educational and social outcomes for students with impairments, offering a theoretical basis for developing targeted interventions.

Key Recommendation: Educational institutions should incorporate strategies to foster self-compassion in students with impairments to promote their academic success and social development.

Keywords: learning Disabilities; self-compassion; systematic literature review

Introduction

Inclusive schools provide new hope for students with special needs. The main goal is to be accepted and build confidence to attend school with regular students in an inclusive class. They are implementing inclusive schools that accept students with obstacles: sight, hearing, and intellect. In practical settings, inclusive schools are predominantly attended by students with learning disabilities. These students face significant challenges in specific academic areas, particularly in reading, writing, and mathematical skills (Kauffman & Hallahan, 2015). The problem is thought to be caused by neurological dysfunction, not intelligence factors (their intelligence is average, and some are even above normal). Students with learning disabilities can have difficulty learning to read (dyslexia), difficulty learning to write (dysgraphia), or difficulty learning to count (dyscalculia). At the same time, in other subjects, they do not experience significant difficulties (Kauffman & Hallahan, 2015).

Students with impairments are individuals who face disruptions in fundamental psychological processes, central nervous system dysfunctions, or neurological disorders, leading to significant difficulties in comprehension, as well as challenges in listening, speaking, reading, spelling, thinking, writing, math, or social skills (Frederickson & Cline, 2014). Intellectual disabilities, emotional disorders, hearing impairments, visual impairments, or factors related to poverty, environment, culture, economy, or instructional mistakes do not cause these challenges. Students with impairments frequently struggle with low self-esteem due to their academic performance, often exhibiting high levels of self-criticism and social withdrawal, which makes it challenging for them to interact with peers (Goad & Parker, 2020). As a result, students with learning disabilities are lazy and have low motivation to increase their academic and non-academic potential.

One way to grow self-confidence and motivation is to increase students' self-compassion. Students with learning disabilities have lower self-compassion scores than regular students (Willoughby & Evans, 2019). This positively correlates with the stress and depression experienced by students, or as one of the study's findings stated, the feeling of being ashamed of the learning environment causes students to decrease their achievements and willingness to learn (Robinson et al., 2018). Davies et al. emphasise that even self-compassion plays a crucial role for students with learning disorders as a considerable factor in fostering self-esteem and motivation (Davies et al., 2021). Students with disorders find it hard to develop self-compassion in their learning process, and putting a focused approach to self-compassion is essential. Self-compassion therapy has been shown to significantly decrease self-criticism among students struggling with disorders (Clapton et al., 2017).

This study reviews the literature on the effects of self-compassion on students with learning disabilities. Self-compassion plays an essential role in improving students' psychological and social well-being, especially those who experience challenges such as self-criticism, stress, and depression. Students with learning disabilities often face negative self-images, which can hinder motivation and self-confidence. With high levels of self-compassion, students can gain the emotional support needed to overcome these obstacles and improve their academic performance and social well-being. Therefore, the results of this study are expected to provide significant contributions to the development of evidence-based intervention programs that can support students with learning disabilities in optimising their academic and social potential more effectively.

Research Objectives

This study aims to fill the gap in the literature by highlighting the benefits of self-compassion as an effective intervention strategy for students with learning disabilities in inclusive educational settings. The focus of this study is to explore how self-compassion can improve academic performance, reduce self-criticism, and strengthen students' social well-being. In addition, this literature review offers a basis for developing innovative tools or technologies designed to enhance self-compassion, in line with the increasing attention to students' mental health in educational contexts.

Method

Research Design

Methods This study conducted a systematic literature review and followed the PRISMA flow diagram for systematic reviews (Moher et al., 2009; Shamseer et al., 2015). The present study aimed to investigate the effect of self-compassion on inclusive school students with impairments. Results from this literature review serve as a basis for developing an intervention model focused on promoting self-compassion among students with disabilities.

Data Search

The literature search relevant to the research objectives was conducted on the Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases for 2016–2022. The selection of these four databases was based on considerations of the quality and validity of the research topic's search results. Google Scholar was used because of its inclusive coverage, covering a variety of peer-reviewed journals and literature sources that may not be indexed in other databases. PubMed was chosen as the primary source specialising in health and psychology, making it very relevant for research on self-compassion interventions in students' mental health. Scopus and Web of Science were chosen because both are highly reputable databases known to have international journal coverage with strict quality standards, thus guaranteeing the validity of the research results (Wilson et al., 2019). The combination of these four databases is expected to provide comprehensive and representative literature coverage, ensuring that all studies relevant to the impact of self-compassion on students with learning disabilities can be identified. Keywords used in the article search included self-compassion, learning disability, learning disabilities, and effect to obtain specific and in-depth results for relevant research.

Study Inclusion and Evaluation Criteria

The inclusion criteria for this study were: (a) investigating the relationship between self-compassion and impairments, (b) being published in a peer-reviewed journal, (c) being written in English, and (d) being released by a reputable publisher. All included articles were reviewed in detail and analysed thematically according to the experimental design.

Study Exclusion and Evaluation Criteria

The excluded studies in this study consisted of qualitative design reports, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, letters, comments, thesis manuscripts, editorials, corrections, reviews, editorials, journal abstracts, conference abstracts, and book chapters. Reviews not included in this study were journal articles that did not discuss the effects of self-compassion on students with learning disabilities. The research results in the journal must be the results of experiments in increasing self-compassion in students with learning disabilities.

Findings

The results of a systematic literature review that has been carried out using the PRISMA model have obtained several journals according to the study criteria sought. In Figure 1, the process of screening journal articles can be seen as follows:

The PRISMA diagram analysis identified 13 articles discussing the impact of increasing self-compassion on students with learning disabilities. The results of this literature review emphasise how vital self-compassion is for these students. This study followed the PRISMA guidelines systematically and transparently to reduce potential bias in source selection. Two researchers independently conducted the selection process, ensuring objectivity and avoiding subjective preferences. Each study was assessed based on pre-determined inclusion and exclusion criteria, so only high-quality and relevant articles were included in the analysis. In addition, search keywords were applied consistently across databases (Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science), reducing the risk of bias that may arise from differences in search terms. These steps ensured more accurate results and represented the research topic well. Table 1 provides a detailed overview of several journals that examine the influence of self-compassion on students with impairments, as outlined below:

Table 1. Study of literature

No	Author	Year	The impact of self-compassion on students with learning disabilities
1	Nemati et al.	2021	Improving the academic outcomes of students with learning disabilities
2	Goad & Parker	2021	Overcoming the problem of self-criticism
3	Davies et al.	2021	Improve social relations around
4	Ghorbani & Jabbari	2020	To reduce depression, stress, anxiety, and possibly other psychological problems in children with learning disabilities
5	Scheffers et al.	2020	Improve social relations
6	Shirani et al.	2020	To increase enthusiasm for learning and reduce feelings of loneliness in students with learning disabilities
7	Pourabdol	2019	To improve social well-being for students with learning disabilities
8	Cowles et al.	2020	Overcoming shyness and self-criticism
9	Robinson et al.	2018	Reduce stress and depression
10	Cebolla et al.	2019	Reduce stress and increase empathy
11	Cooper & Frearson.	2017	Reduce self-criticism and increase self-confidence in learners with learning disabilities.
12	Wagner et al.	2017	Self-compassion can provide a self-understanding of one's abilities in classroom learning.
13	Clapton et al.	2017	Decreased self-criticism in learning disabilities

The literature study results showed self-compassion's impact on students with learning disabilities. Can be cited as a theoretical basis for the effects of self-compassion on students with learning disabilities, namely (1) improving academic achievement in school, (2) overcoming self-criticism, (3) reducing stress, depression, anxiety, and loneliness, (4) increasing self-confidence, (5) increase the spirit of learning, and (6) improve social well-being. Self-compassion has a powerful impact on the learning and social engagement of students with learning disabilities. The results of this study can be followed up to provide interventions, therapy, and services to increase self-compassion so that students with learning disabilities can develop according to their abilities.

Discussion

Self-compassion involves offering support and kindness to oneself during suffering, failure, and imperfection rather than self-criticism (Ariyani & Hadiani, 2019). This ability is crucial for individuals to adapt and thrive in their surroundings. It is a concept that reflects the tendency to acknowledge both strengths and weaknesses when encountering challenging situations (Wagner et al., 2017). In student psychology, the presence of self-compassion can reduce the effect of stress, depression, and environmental pressure (Fong & Loi, 2016). When a person shows self-acceptance, compassion, and tolerance, it can be called self-compassion (Azeem & Al-Abyadh, 2021). Self-compassion can be significantly increased in an educational environment that teaches students to be themselves, to be grateful, and to be mindful (Ariyani & Hadiani, 2019). Low self-compassion is associated with problems in various areas in

students with learning disabilities, incredibly emotional (Abooei et al., 2021; Al-Awamleh, 2020)

The notable academic impact is reflected in improving students' performance in school (Nemati et al., 2021). Self-compassion has the potential to boost a sense of personal vitality and decrease feelings of isolation among students with learning disabilities (Shirani et al., 2020). This therapeutic training effectively supports students' mental well-being (Kotera & Gordon, 2021). Self-compassion-based interventions can be explored in educational contexts to help students reduce academic-related stress (Zhang et al., 2016). Parents, teachers, and peers at school provide support as the surrounding social environment is essential in the self-compassionate intervention process. With this support, self-compassion development will accelerate, helping students with learning disabilities in inclusive schools to address their challenges more effectively. Activities that can increase self-compassion are doing physical exercise in the gym (Hallion et al., 2019). Doing exercise every morning can provide motivation and make you feel respect for yourself for the health you get (Thakur & Joshi, 2016).

Increasing self-compassion can be done with gratitude training activities to provide an understanding of gratitude and increase gratitude and self-compassion. This training is divided into two meetings, each into several sessions (Ridwan et al., 2021). According to several previous studies, activities that can foster self-acceptance, social and physical, have been proven to be very effective in increasing self-compassion. Activities can be done two times a week for students with special needs. Another activity that can be done in the classroom to foster self-compassion in students with learning disabilities is to use fun learning methods by singing and playing (Wagner et al., 2017). These activities can be applied to students with learning disabilities to increase self-compassion, motivation, and confidence in learning in inclusive schools (Long & Neff, 2018). The increase in self-compassion in students with learning disabilities is very quickly assisted by activities carried out by students designed by teachers and parents beforehand, which assess the baseline level of self-compassion in students with impairments.

This study is an essential contribution to understanding how self-compassion can be critical in supporting students with learning disabilities, especially in inclusive educational environments. The findings of this study indicate that self-compassion not only plays a role in improving academic performance but also helps strengthen students' social skills. Through this study, schools and educational institutions can begin integrating programs that focus on developing self-compassion as part of psychological support for students. On the other hand, this research also opens up opportunities for developing innovative technology-based tools and training programs designed to improve self-compassion to help students with disabilities overcome emotional challenges and optimise their learning potential.

Conclusion

The findings from a literature review of 13 articles highlighted the impact of self-compassion on students with impairments. These results can be utilised as a theoretical foundation for the benefits of self-compassion on these students, which include (1) enhancing academic performance, (2) reducing self-criticism, (3) alleviating issues related to stress, depression, anxiety, and loneliness, (4) boosting self-confidence, (5) fostering a tremendous enthusiasm for learning, and (6) improving social well-being. Self-compassion's significant influence extends to learning and social experiences for impaired students. The study's findings suggest that interventions, therapies, and support services should be developed to enhance self-

compassion, enabling students with impairments to grow according to their potential. Effective self-compassion interventions require support from the broader social environment, including parents, teachers, and peers. With such backing, self-compassion development will be more rapid, allowing students with impairments in inclusive settings to navigate their challenges better. Activities that can foster social and physical self-acceptance are proven to be very effective in increasing self-compassion, such as sports, gratitude training, and learning in inclusive classes by singing and playing.

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